

Demonstration of Power Exhaust Control by Impurity Seeding in the Island Divertor of Wendelstein 7-X

F. Effenberg^a, S. Brezinsek^b, Y. Feng^c, M. Jakubowski^c, R. König^c, M. Krychowiak^c, H. Niemann^c, V. Perseo^c, O. Schmitz^a, D. Zhang^c, A. Ali^c, T. Barbui^a, C. Biedermann^c, R. Burhenn^c, B. Buttenschön^c, P. Drewelow^c, H. Frerichs^a, Y. Gao^c, J. Geiger^c, C. Killer^c, D. Gradic^c, G. Kocsis^e, M. Otte^c, A. Puig Sitjes^c, F. Reimold^c, L. Rudischhauser^c, T. Sunn Pedersen^c, Y. Suzuki^d, T. Szepesi^e, V. Winters^a, G.A. Wurden^f and the W7-X Team

a – University of Wisconsin – Madison, Department of Engineering Physics, Madison, WI, USA

b – IEK 4, Forschungszentrum Jülich GmbH, Association EURATOM-FZJ, 52425 Jülich, Germany

c – Max-Planck-Institut für Plasmaphysik, Association EURATOM-IPP, 17491 Greifswald, Germany

d – National Institute for Fusion Science, 322-6 Oroshi-cho, Toki 509-5292, Japan

e – Wigner Research Center for Physics, H-1121, Budapest, Hungary

f – Los Alamos National Laboratory, PO Box 1663, Los Alamos, NM 87545, USA

Acknowledgement: This work was funded by the Department of Energy under grant DE-SC0014210 and by the College of Engineering at the University of Madison, Wisconsin. The effort has been carried out within the framework of the EUROfusion Consortium and has received funding from the Euratom research and training program 2014-2018 under grant agreement No 633053. The views and opinions expressed herein do not necessarily reflect those of the European Commission.

**27th IAEA Fusion Energy Conference,
Mahatma Mandir, Gandhinagar, India,
22-27 October, 2018**

Contact:
effenberg@wisc.edu

EUROfusion

College of Engineering
UNIVERSITY OF WISCONSIN-MADISON

Power exhaust and impurity seeding in the 3D island divertor

Effects of Neon and Nitrogen seeding

Impact of island geometry on power exhaust

Power exhaust and impurity seeding in the 3D island divertor

Effects of Neon and Nitrogen seeding

Impact of island geometry on power exhaust

Power exhaust is a 3D issue in the perspective of quasi-stationary high performance operation

Mitigation of 3D heat fluxes on highly shaped divertor poses a specific challenge

Measured vs modeled heat flux:

- T. Sunn Pedersen et al. EX/9-1
- M. Jakubowski et al. EX/P8-16
- J. D. Lore et al. EX/P8-19

Local impurity seeding in 3D island divertor

Island divertor: efficient for impurity exhaust and screening

3D modeling: the island geometry determines the power and particle exhaust

Scrape-off layer (SOL):
islands with long connection
lengths: $L_c \sim O(100 \text{ m})$

SOL heat transport
concentrated
around island separatrix

Counter-streaming
convective heat and
particle fluxes

F. Effenberg et al. submitted to JNM

Y. Feng et al 2006 Nucl. Fusion **46** 807

Power exhaust and impurity seeding in the 3D island divertor

Effects of Neon and Nitrogen seeding

Impact of island geometry on power exhaust

Short Neon injections causes rapid and sustained radiative power enhancement

#20180920.042

Impurity Spectroscopy: Ne recycles in divertor after injection

Visible line emission

NeI @ 640.2nm

Neon seeding causes uniform reduction of divertor heat loads as predicted by 3D modeling

Measured heat fluxes (IR):

Modelled heat fluxes (EMC3-EIRENE):

$$n_{\text{sep}} = 10^{19} \text{ m}^{-3}, P = 4 \text{ MW}, D_{\perp} = \chi_{\perp} = 1 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}, \Gamma_{\text{Ne}} \sim c(f_{\text{rad}}) \Gamma_{\text{rec}}$$

Global reduction of divertor heat and particle fluxes accompanied by degrading neutral pressure

- Uniform and sustained cooling & power detachment on all divertors
- Particle fluxes reduce
- Neutral pressure decreases

Neon seeding reduces counter streaming flows in agreement with modeling

Doppler Coherence Imaging Spectroscopy (CIS)

Cooling effects on SOL flows:

$$V_{\parallel, C+2} \sim F_{\text{fric, imp}} \sim V_{\parallel}$$

$$V_{\parallel} \sim T_e^{0.5}$$

$$\Gamma_{\parallel} = n V_{\parallel}$$

$$q_{\parallel, \text{conv}} \sim T_e \Gamma_{\parallel} \sim T_e^{3/2}$$

Modelled flows (EMC3-EIRENE)

V. Perseo et al APS Conference 2018
D. Gradic et al 2018 PPCF **60** 084007

Nitrogen seeding: low recycling requires continuous seeding recovery due to low recycling

Impurity spectroscopy:
 N_2 line emission decays after injection

N_2 seeded limiter plasma

T. Barbui & F. Effenberg et al.

Nitrogen seeding: slow radiation enhancement and recovery due to low recycling

- Heat and particle fluxes reduce on all divertors, but slight asymmetries
 - Asymmetric neutral pressure response
- 3D effects on N_2 seeding?

Power exhaust and impurity seeding in the 3D island divertor

Effects of Neon and Nitrogen seeding

Impact of island geometry on power exhaust

Change island geometry with control coils to investigate impact on power exhaust

Island widths increased with control coils

Island connection lengths reduce

Heat and particle exhaust enhanced due to reduced connection lengths

→ Shift and concentration of q_{div} and Γ_{div} :

$$\lambda_q \sim L_C^{0.5}, \quad \tau_p \sim L_C / v_{\parallel}$$

Radiated power level and exhaust change in response to island geometry change

$$P_{\text{rad}}(t) \sim \exp(-t/\tau_{\text{rad}})$$

→

$$\tau_{\text{rad}} \sim 547 \text{ms}$$

$$\tau_{\text{rad}} \sim 237 \text{ms}$$

→ Power exhaust can be controlled by island shaping

→ Mimics **higher β** effects on island geometry predicted by 3D MHD codes (e.g. VMEC, HINT)

Y Suzuki and J Geiger 2016 Plasma Phys. Control. Fusion **58** 064004
F. Effenberg et al. submitted to Nuclear Materials & Energy

Local impurity seeding enhances edge radiative power and reduces heat and particle fluxes

Ne: high recycling radiator, uniform radiative power exhaust

N₂: low recycling, 3D effects on cooling, indication of better neutral compression

Change of island geometry is an additional actuator for power exhaust control

Seeding combined with manipulation of island geometry promising for power exhaust control in high-performance divertor scenarios at W7-X

APPENDIX

Demonstration of Power Exhaust Control by Impurity Seeding in the Island Divertor of Wendelstein 7-X

- stable high radiation scenarios with $f_{\text{rad}} = 70\% - 80\%$ and mostly uniformly reduced q_{div} and Γ_{div}
- Ne: effective radiator, high recycling
- N₂: low recycling, better neutral compression
- Island geometry: an additional actuator for power exhaust control

Divertor heat fluxes #20180920.042

power flux

radiative power

Impurity seeding combined with manipulation of island geometry promising for power exhaust control in high-performance divertor scenarios at W7-X

EMC3-EIRENE is a 3D plasma fluid and kinetic neutral edge transport Monte Carlo code

ENERGY

$$\nabla \cdot \left(\frac{\xi}{2} n_e T_e V_{\parallel} \mathbf{b} - \kappa_e \nabla_{\parallel} T_e - \frac{\xi}{2} T_e D \nabla_{\perp} n_e - \chi_e n_e \nabla_{\perp} T_e \right) = -k(T_e - T_i) + S_{ee} + S_{imp}$$

$$\nabla \cdot \left(\frac{\xi}{2} n_i T_i V_{\parallel} \mathbf{b} - \kappa_i \nabla_{\parallel} T_i - \frac{\xi}{2} T_i D \nabla_{\perp} n_i - \chi_i n_i \nabla_{\perp} T_i \right) = +k(T_e - T_i) + S_{ei}$$

STREAMING

$$\nabla \cdot (n_i V_{\parallel} \mathbf{b} - D \nabla_{\perp} n_i) = S_p$$

$$\nabla \cdot (m_i n_i V_{\parallel} V_{\parallel} \mathbf{b} - \eta_{\parallel} \nabla_{\parallel} V_{\parallel} - m_i D \nabla_{\perp} n_i V_{\parallel}) = -\nabla_{\parallel} p + S_m$$

IMPURITY

$$\nabla \cdot (n_i^z V_{\parallel}^z \mathbf{b} - D_i^z \nabla_{\perp} n_i^z) = S_{z-1 \rightarrow z} - S_{z \rightarrow z+1} + R_{z+1 \rightarrow z} - R_{z \rightarrow z-1}$$

$$U_{ii}^z (V_{\parallel}^z - V_{\parallel}) = -\mathbf{b} \cdot \nabla n_i^z T_i^z + n_i^z Z_e E_{\parallel} + n_i^z Z^2 C_e \mathbf{b} \cdot \nabla T_e + n_i^z C_i \mathbf{b} \cdot \nabla T_i$$

NEUTRAL

Neutral transport/EIRENE

Y. Feng et al 2004, Contrib. Plasma Phys., **44**: 57-69,
 D. Reiter et al 2005., Fusion Sci. and Techn. **47** 172–186

Distribution of intrinsic radiative losses determined by radiation potential and source location

Measured radiated power

Tomographic inversion:
S. Kwak & J. Svensson

Modelled radiated power

W7-X has a C divertor and wall interface: → intrinsic radiation potentials are comparable to N₂

A. Kallenbach et al., Journal of Nucl. Mat., 415(1), 2011

The radiation potential L_Z and the recycling characteristics make a difference for the radiation location and time dependence

Low recycling and local cooling effects of N_2 has been demonstrated in W7-X limiter plasmas

In preparation (for publication) by T. Barbui & F. Effenberg et al.

N₂ injection shows weak and short response Prad and in edge cooling

#20171207.048

$$\Gamma_N \sim 1.4 \cdot 10^{21} \text{ e}^-/\text{s}$$

$$\Delta P_{rad} \sim +40\%$$

$$\Delta W_{dia} \sim +0\%, \Delta \tau_E \sim +0\%$$

T_e by He beam

q_{div} by IR

Stable power exhaust with Neon seeding in lower performance scenarios

#20171207.045

Divertor seeding

$$\Gamma_{\text{Ne}} \sim 5 \cdot 10^{19} \text{ s}^{-1}$$

$$\Delta P_{\text{rad}} \sim +90\%$$

$$\Delta W_{\text{dia}} \sim +0\%$$

$$\Delta \tau_E \sim +0\%$$

#20171207.045

$\tau_{\text{Ne inj.}} = 400 \text{ ms}$

3D modeling approach: radiation localized in island center during divertor Ne and N seeding

Carbon: $f_{\text{rad}} = 20\%$

erosion

Neon: $f_{\text{rad}} = 40\%$

recycling

Nitrogen: $f_{\text{rad}} = 40\%$

puff

$$n_{\text{up}} = 1 \cdot 10^{19} \text{ m}^{-3}, P = 2.5 \text{ MW}, D_{\perp} = 0.5 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}, \chi_{\perp} = 3 D_{\perp}$$

$$\rightarrow \Gamma_{\text{Ne}} = 1.1 \cdot 10^{21} \text{ s}^{-1}, \Gamma_{\text{N}} = 2.0 \cdot 10^{21} \text{ s}^{-1}$$